

DMS Impact Survey

This survey aims to assess the efficacy and long-term impact of the Data Market Services programme.

Your responses will be used to fine tune the services that we offer, as well as helping us to demonstrate the wider economic and social outcomes of our programme to the European Commission. This will help public funders to understand why DMS makes a difference and hopefully continue to fund similar programmes in the future.

Your input is extremely important to us!

* Required

1. Your name *

2. Your email address *

3. Your company name *

4. Looking back on your experience at DMS, please rate these business activities according to how much they benefited from your participation in the programme

*

Mark only one oval per row.

	1 - benefited least	2	3	4	5 - benefited most
Promoting your company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fundraising	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Upskilling your workforce	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data compliance and management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IP management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Entrepreneurial skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploring international markets	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Market impact

Your sales capacity

Sales capacity refers to your ability to serve new clients. This can include improved efficiency in logistics, human resources or utilisation of new technical assets.

5. Has the sales capacity of your company increased since participating DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

6. If yes, please provide the estimated increase in % and specify what has improved.

7. Has your revenue increased since participating in DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

8. If yes, please provide the estimated increase in %

9. Did you gain any new clients as a result of having participated in DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

10. If yes, how many?

11. Could you name one way DMS has helped you increase your market impact?

Fundraising

12. Have you gained any additional funding since participating in DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

13. If yes, please specify the amount, public or private, and number of rounds

14. Could you name one way DMS has helped you increase your fundraising abilities?

Innovation

15. Have you developed any new products, datasets or services since participating in DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

16. If yes, please specify the type of solution (e.g. dataset, cloud service, mobile app), and whether you applied for IPR (e.g. patent, trademark)

17. We are interested to know if your company's approach to data management has been influenced by DMS training. Please indicate which areas have improved

Social Impact

18. Has your team grown since you participated in DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

19. If yes, please tell us how many new members have joined your team and their position/role within your company

20. Has the gender composition of your team changed? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

21. If yes, please give us a % breakdown of before/after. (e.g. Before 75% female, 25% male. After 60% female, 40% male)

22. Have you pursued any new collaborations or partnerships? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

23. Could you name one way DMS has helped you increase your social impact?

Your Success

24. Would you like to share a success story or testimonial so that we can help give you visibility?

25. How likely are you to recommend DMS to other startups? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not likely Extremely likely

26. Looking back on your experience at DMS, is there anything we could have done better to support your business?

Thank you very much for completing this survey, we appreciate your response!

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